

TOWARDS URBAN STRATEGY FOR THE NATIONAL PROJECTS MANAGEMENT IN EGYPT

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Abstract

This research revolves around national projects in Egypt till a proposed strategy for managing national projects in Egypt. It is divided into three parts. Part one reviews all concepts and definitions related to the project, such as: project definition, project planning, projects and strategic planning, project management, and concepts and definitions related to strategy, such as: the definition of strategy and criteria for using the strategy term, then the research moves to national projects in Egypt, starting with the definition of national projects, criteria for defining national projects, their types and characteristics, and then national projects in Egypt throughout history. The second part contained an analysis of the existing national projects in Egypt, whether they were before or after Egypt's Vision 2030, with a study of global models of strategic management in order to gain an integrated understanding of the management of national projects. The third part is the development of an urban strategy for managing national projects in Egypt and setting the main frameworks for it. The proposed strategy for managing national projects is divided into three main sections according to the project phases: the pre-project implementation phase, the project implementation phase, and the post-project implementation phase.

Keywords: Project, Project management, Strategy, National project.

INTRODUCTION

National projects are topics that have received significant attention from the government in recent years due to their effective and tangible impact on the achievement of economic and social development goals. Their effects extend beyond the economic level to social, political, and environmental aspects, so their studies and strategies must be updated on a regular basis. The main characteristics of national mega-projects are their inclusiveness, expansion, and spread across the country. This contributes to economic balance; the establishment of comprehensive social justice; the reduction of unemployment and poverty; and the redistribution and spread of the population across the Republic's regions through a series of new cities.

Define a research problem:

Egypt as a developing country faces a lot of problems and challenges that hinder development, therefore, the state has recently moved to develop a lot of strategies to solve those problems and challenges, most of which have not been updated so far, in addition, through the study of national projects in Egypt since the beginning of the era of the Republic until now, it turned out that there are many visions, strategies and goals for national projects that differ according to the studies that contained them, and they are not united by a single, comprehensive vision, unified strategies and goals, despite the stability of the place, and they may be united by some common axes and strengths, but they may be marred by some shortcomings, either in defining

goals and studies necessary for projects or in the implementation of And follow up on those projects.

The research goals:

The research aims primarily to develop a strategy for managing national projects in Egypt, based on previous national projects carried out by the state as one of the most important experiences in national projects, as well as on the experiences of different countries in national projects and their management, in order to capitalise on previous national projects' strengths and potential while avoiding shortcomings. The vision does not end with theoretical studies.

The research hypothesis:

Based on the previous research problems, a hypothesis for the study can be developed that states: "the development of a proposed strategy for managing national projects in Egypt increases the efficiency of these national projects and increases the possibility of achieving the goals for which they were established."

THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The research methodology relied on a variety of approaches, beginning with the "inductive theoretical approach" to review all concepts and definitions related to the project, such as: project definition, project planning, projects, strategic planning, project management, concepts and definitions related to strategy, such as: the definition of strategy and criteria for using the term strategy, before moving on to the study of national projects in Egypt, st

The research then moves on to the "analytical approach," which is divided into three sections: the first section: analysis of existing national projects in Egypt that were implemented prior to the development of Egypt's Vision 2030 by measuring the percentage of achievement of those projects to their goals; the second section: analysis of national projects in Egypt's Vision 2030 by identifying the objectives of those projects as a definition, and then identification of those projects as a definition, and then identification of those projects as a The third section is about global models of strategic management, in which planning and strategic thinking were studied in many countries, such as the United States, France, Australia, Russia, Morocco, Kenya, and then national projects in South Korea to determine the benefits.

The third approach is the "deductive approach," which was used to develop an urban strategy for managing national projects in Egypt and establish the main frameworks for them.

1. Project:

1.1 Project Definition: The following are the most important project definitions:

- A project is a short-term effort to achieve specific goals at a specific time.
- A project is defined as a short-term activity initiated to produce a one-of-a-kind product, service, or result.

1.2 Project Management:

1.2.1 Project Management Concept:

Project management is the process of correctly directing resources and material and human resources using modern methods to achieve the objectives in a way that contributes to the completion of the project, taking into account the factors of quality, time, and cost, as the components of any project are scope, time, and cost, and project management includes:

- Specify needs.
- Establish specific and attainable goals.
- Maintain a competitive balance of quality, scope, time, and cost.
- Tailoring the specifications, plans, and style to the various interests and expectations of the project's many stakeholders.

1-2-2 Importance of Project Management:

The importance of the project management process is summarized in four variables as follows:

First: contribute to saving time and not depending on chance.

Second: making forecasts for the future and what surprises and fluctuations it may bring.

Third: coordinating the efforts of the project staff.

Fourth: providing performance measures and standards.

Fifth: obtaining a schematic representation of the project.

Sixth: distinguish between critical and non-critical tasks in the project.

1.2.3 Elements of effective project management:

The success of project management requires the availability of some basic elements, as follows:

- 1- Inlusiveness: the management should cover the various fields and activities of the project, and not be limited to one aspect only, and the project management engineer should give appropriate attention to each field (in the contracting company) or activity (in the project), unless circumstances require otherwise.
- 2- Clarity: The project plan's implementation requires clarity and simplicity in order to be easily understood and accepted by the technical staff who will implement it, and thus each individual and group understands its tasks, role, and what is expected of it.
- 3- Realism: the planning must be consistent and compatible with the reality of the contracting company's internal and external conditions in general and the project to be implemented in particular, while staying away from excessive and unreasonable optimism or pessimism.
- 4- The planner/planning engineer must anticipate changes in internal or external conditions in the company or project, which necessitates the development of flexible plans that can be adjusted in response to changing circumstances.

- 5- Specificity: the more specific the planning is and the goals and activities are formulated accurately without generalities, the greater the chances of successful implementation of the plan.
- 6- Integration and homogeneity between plans and objectives: the success of planning requires achieving compatibility and integration between all types of plans and objectives, between strategies, tactical plans, operational plans and between long -, medium- and short-term plans, as for engineering project planning, integration and homogeneity is achieved by reconciling all elements of the project and achieving a balance between the duration of the project, the cost of the project and the degree of quality of implementation

2- The strategy:

2.1 Definition of strategy:

Strategy is a concept of Greek origin that was crystallized and developed in the military field, "it means the art of leading the forces and military resources available to confront the enemy," and this concept was developed in the field of contracting in the USA in the Sixties.

Michael Porter defines the strategy as: it works to find a comfortable position for the benefit of the organization, it is a strategy that seeks to adopt permanent profitability in the midst of the forces that form the competitive framework of the sector, and in order for the collective councils to achieve their development role at the local level in the medium and long term, it is required to combine the concepts of planning and strategy, and thus we are in front of the strategic planning methodology.

Strategy is also defined as being about two things: where do we want to go and how to get there in order to effectively deal with urban planning issues, which are often complex and influenced by a wide range of spatial, social and environmental factors, in this case, well-prepared long-term strategies must be available.

Figure No: 1 determining the areas of the strategy

The concept of strategy has been adapted from the military fields and adapted for use in planning. In planning and management, as in the military fields, the strategy aims to bridge the gap between the goals and the operational steps, that is, the strategies work to achieve

communication between the ends and means. It should be noted that the strategy is concerned with how to achieve the goals and objectives in the form of principles and rules that we will implement. In other words, the strategies themselves are not concerned with what these goals and mechanisms are or what they should be or how they were developed, but it is concerned with how to achieve the vision and goals.

2.2 Criteria for the use of the term Strategy:

Everything that characterizes the strategy must meet the following criteria:

- 1- The use of the term "strategy" may be limited to everything prepared, planned, or handled by the higher leadership or administrative level in any organization, provided that it is responsible for defining and achieving the goals of the organization.
- 2- Assignment of tasks, identification of responsibilities and stages: planning to achieve a direct goal that is achieved at the same planned level is not characterized by a strategy. Therefore, the strategic plan must result in a division of goals, assignment of tasks, and distribution of roles for the middle and lower levels. With depending on these tasks, these levels are new and separate plans to achieve, with which, with the sum of their successes, the goal is achieved. If these minimum plans do not exist, there is no way to describe the plan as a strategy because it loses the element of division of roles and cooperation and thus loses the ability to maneuver.

The strategy is one of the coming five stages of strategic planning preparation:

The first stage: organize efforts.

The second stage: research the current situation.

The third stage: strategy development.

The fourth stage: strategy implementation.

The fifth stage: strategy evaluation.

3- National projects:

3.1 National project definition:

The most important of these definitions is discussed in the following lines:

According to one definition, giant national projects are distinguished by their comprehensiveness, breadth, and spread across the country, and this, in some ways, contributes to providing a strong impetus to the movement of economic activity, attracting foreign investments, increasing job opportunities for young people, achieving economic balance, reducing unemployment and poverty, establishing integrated urban communities, and then redistributing.

A second definition says that what is meant by national projects is mega projects, and in the international custom, a project is considered a giant if the volume of its investments exceeds one billion dollars with multiple positive effects on the economy and the environment and the extension of those effects for many generations to come, with the need for economic and social feasibility of the project.

A third definition says that a mega-project is an investment project on a very large scale, and a project can be defined as a giant if its cost exceeds one billion US dollars, and attracts a lot of public attention because of its significant impact on a common community, a natural environment or a state budget. A giant project can be defined as an initiative implemented on the ground, very expensive, and public.

Others define it as a project that meets the aspirations of a broad base of the people and efficiently links the roles of the state, the private sector, civil society, and international investment in comprehensive development. This definition confirms a fundamental fact, namely the need for integration between the state, the private sector, and civil society.

The national project is also defined as a project that does not belong to anyone, but is the project of all the people, and it is also characterized as not single-purpose, but multi-purpose, and is not limited to the economic aspect, but goes beyond it in many aspects.

National projects are also defined as a strategic vision for society's development in a subsequent era, which is experiencing a qualitative shift and radical far-reaching changes affecting people, places, and material and cultural resources.

It also introduces another definition of the concept of the national project as a concept concerned with the pillars and origins of building a new, rising and advanced society, and this project does not acquire its national character by a government decision at any level, or by propaganda for it, but acquires that character from the compatibility of the objectives of the national project with the interests of the majority of society members.

From the above, the national project can be defined as that large project, physically and cadastral, service or investment, the decision to implement it is taken by the highest levels of management, implemented by a large number of workers in many fields, and benefited by a large number of people, and its return is large materially and service, and often it is one of the tools of the state to advance its economy. In addition, projects are the executive tool of various policies in various sectors, and there is no equivalent at the state level.

3-2 The criteria for national projects: based on the foregoing:

- 1- The decision to implement them should be taken by the highest levels of the administration of the state.
- 2- To be large Cadastral and material (in construction projects).
- 3- It is based on the implementation of a large number of executors.
- 4- Its benefits accrue to a large number of people.

3-3 Types of National Projects:

There are many types of national projects that can be summarised in:

- 1- Construction projects, which require the provision of land areas and also require construction, such as: the project to establish the new administrative capital and the Suez Canal Axis development project.

- 2- Projects in the form of programs, initiatives, or administrative decisions such as: reforming the legislative environment to improve the investment climate and turning Egypt into a digital hub.

In this study, attention will be paid to urban construction projects as the most projects to which the previous definition applies, so we do not include projects such as social initiatives or administrative decisions and others.

3.4 Characteristics of national projects:

The most important characteristics and dimensions of national projects can be summarized as follows:

- 1- Attracting human energies and supporting loyalty and belonging: as it represents a public popular dream, the achievement of this goal is supported by the availability of a range of social services, such as education and health care, which coincide with the economic aspects of national projects.
- 2- Making a qualitative leap in development rates: This is achieved through the simultaneous contributions of industrial, agricultural, extractive and service activities.
- 3- Work out a balance in the pattern and distribution of investments, and the return of development between the different regions and governorates.
- 4- Achieving a national production goal through the future weight of investments and their spatial sectoral distributions.
- 5- The investment dimension lies in the nature of projects between infrastructure and urban development and the corresponding social services and human development, in addition to investments in various fields.
- 6- Diversity of development areas: This is achieved through the pursuit of projects to achieve comprehensive integrated development.
- 7- Achieving vertical and horizontal development: Achieving vertical development comes with the types of projects in terms of horizontal development through horizontal expansion in urban development to create a kind of balance between different regions.

3.5 National projects in Egypt throughout history:

Pharaonic era: The temples and pyramids built in the Pharaonic era can be considered national projects, and the construction of these pyramids and temples, although they served as houses of worship or tombs for kings to preserve their bodies and ensure their immortality in the other world, was not intended to serve society, but they were the largest at that time, employed a lot of labour over many years, and used the latest technologies available at that time. The descendants of the Pharaohs benefited from these projects. The ancient Egyptian pyramids and temples in our time have become a tourist project that guarantees Egypt a strong economy.

The Greek era: The Ptolemaist built palaces and gardens in Alexandria; Alexandria became the centre of civilization, where it became famous in the fields of art, science, industry, and

trade; and it was the first port in the Mediterranean Sea thanks to its famous lighthouse, which the Greeks considered one of the Seven Wonders of the World. Alexandria was built by a great Greek civilization:

The University of Alexandria (ancient) was established by the Ptolemaist. Thanks to the scientists of the University of Alexandria in reaching scientific facts about the rotation of the earth around the sun and the earth's ocean, the university was famous for medicine, especially anatomy and surgery.

The Library of Alexandria and its cultural impact: the Ptolemaist established a huge library in Alexandria, which was considered the greatest library in the world, and which contained more than half a million papyrus scrolls. The Ptolemaist ordered each visiting scholar to give the city of Alexandria a copy of his works, bringing the number of books in the library to more than 700,000 books. The Ptolemaist built many temples, such as the temple of Edfu, the temple of Dendera, and the temples of Philae in Aswan.

-Roman era: The Romans entered Egypt in 30 BC. The ancient university of Alexandria continued to function, and Egypt was well-known for its production of glass, paper, linen, perfumes, and decorative items.

Coptic era: Christianity entered Egypt in the middle of the first century AD, with the entry of St. Mark to Alexandria and the establishment of the First Church in Egypt and all of Africa.

Islamic eras: Islam entered Egypt in 641 ad. During the period of Arab-Islamic rule, Egypt witnessed progress in the fields of architecture and arts, such as Islamic style architecture and inscriptions. Many mosques, castles, and fences were built. In the Fatimid era, the Al-Azhar mosque was considered the most famous work of architecture during the Fatimid Caliphate in Egypt. In the Ayyub era, Saladin Castle was built, which is the most famous fortress in the city of Cairo, in addition to the architectural wealth that appeared in the Mamluk era of mosques, schools, agencies, and others.

Alawite family: Muhammad Ali began building a strong Egyptian army and establishing a military school; the shipbuilding industry arose in Bulaq and the naval arsenal in Alexandria; reformed agricultural and irrigation conditions; established canals such as charity canals; dams and canals; factories and laboratories; and in the field of trade, Muhammad Ali Pasha worked to spread security to internal trade routes and create a foreign trade fleet where trade was conducted.

In the following eras, the country witnessed a renaissance represented by administrative reform; industry and agriculture witnessed a renaissance and great prosperity; the Khedive Opera House was established; the railway lines were extended; and in 1869, the Suez Canal was opened for international navigation in a great celebration.

The Republic: The 1952 revolution carried out many tasks, the most important of which was the issuance of the agrarian reform law; the first five-year plan for economic and social development in the history of Egypt was developed in 1960; the attempt to develop industry and production; the establishment of sugar, oil, soap, aluminum, iron, cement, and dairy

factories; the nationalization of the Suez Canal; and the construction of the High Dam, which is the most important development project in the world in the 21st century.

Then the idea of creating new cities and the Ring Road around Cairo appeared, then the national projects increased, so many new cities were established, and the projects of Toshka and Sharq Al-Owainat appeared, then the new Suez Canal, the administrative capital, and many factories in all fields.

According to this narrative, the most similar national projects to the current projects being carried out by the Egyptian state are those that occurred during the establishment of the Egyptian republic, and thus these projects will be discussed in some detail.

3-6 National projects during the Egyptian Republic's establishment: The Egyptian Republic's establishment was characterized by an abundance and diversity of projects that the country required at the time, but we will only deal with urban projects, the most prominent of which are:

- 1- The Islamic city of Ba'ath in Cairo.
- 2- Nasser sports stadium (currently Cairo International Stadium).
- 3- Helwan aircraft factory.
- 4- Egyptian automobile factory (Nasr).
- 5- The Egyptian chemical company (Kema).
- 6- Misr Chemical Industry
- 7- Helwan Iron and Steel Company
- 8- The Egyptian nuclear reactor in Inshas.
- 9- The High Dam.
- 10- Nasser Bridge (currently October 6).
- 11- Cairo Tower (Al Jazeera Tower).
- 12- Nile Corniche in Cairo.
- 13- Egyptian television channel.
- 14- Nag Hammadi aluminium complex.
- 15- Railway waggon factory (simaf).
- 16- Dairy plants.
- 17- New cities
- 18- Sharq al-Owainat project.
- 19- Toshka spillway
- 20- The subway.

3-7 Analysis of existing national projects in Egypt:

To analyze previous national projects in Egypt (projects prior to the development of Egypt's Vision 2030), the extent to which these projects achieved their goals was studied; a relative weight was placed on each of the project's goals, measuring the extent to which it was achieved, and then determining the total percentage of achieving the project's goals.

Table No: 1 the average percentage of achieving the objectives of existing national projects in Egypt

Project	The percentage of achieving project goals	Project	The percentage of achieving project goals
The Islamic city of Ba'ath in Cairo	100	Nile Corniche in Cairo	100
Nasser sports stadium (currently Cairo International Stadium)	100	Egyptian television channel	100
Helwan aircraft factory	30	Nag Hammadi aluminium complex	100
Egyptian automobile factory (Nasr)	60	Railway waggon factory (simaf)	100
The Egyptian chemical company (Kema)	100	Dairy plants	70
Misr Chemical Industry	100	New cities	83
Helwan Iron and Steel Company	100	Sharq al-Owainat project	10
The Egyptian nuclear reactor in Inshas	50	Toshka spillway	35
The High Dam	100	The subway	100
Nasser Bridge (currently October 6)	90	The general average of the percentage of achieving the objectives of national projects	81.4%
Cairo Tower (Al Jazeera Tower)	100		

From the above it is clear that the general average of the percentage of achieving the objectives of the existing national projects in Egypt that were established during the period of the Egyptian Republic, even before the establishment of Egypt's Vision 2030, amounted to 81.4%. It is also clear that there is a common factor that brings together the previous national projects, which is that they didn't have a unique vision that unique those to achieve sectoral goals, which in turn achieve vision goals that were previously set. In fact, the strategy used in most of these projects arose because of the absolute need for these projects or out of a motive to achieve a certain competitive advantage or solve a specific problem. Each project was studied separately in terms of its components, implementation capabilities and financing. Its study has been completed, it has just been implemented,

Some of these projects lacked modernization and keeping up with developments, which is a necessary feature that must be available in any project, which led some of them to extinction and end, and if any projects do not take into account the possibility of modernization and development, they will end as some of them did.

3.8 National Project Objectives in Egypt: The following are the objectives of most national projects:

- 1- Addressing the regional imbalances witnessed by the development centre in the narrow valley strip, which does not exceed an area of 6%, through which it is possible to stop the migration movement from the southern governorates to the Delta governorates.
- 2- With the steady population increase and concentrating it in a built-up area not exceeding 6% of the total area of the Republic, and with the expected increase in the population, it became necessary to absorb this increase in major national projects and to achieve the connection

between the desert governorates and the rest of the world through transport, electricity and communications networks, targeted service centers, as well as bridges and tunnels projects to connect Sinai and the eastern parts of the Canal governorates, Cairo and Delta governorates.

- 3- Increasing the productive efficiency of the economic resources held by the state
- 4- Correcting the severe imbalances in the pattern and distribution of investments and the return of development between the different regions and governorates of Egypt, thereby reducing economic and social disparities, achieving balanced development and exploiting the possibilities available on the land of Egypt, and preparing new areas for projects and the population.
- 5- Achieving comprehensive integrated development such as agricultural, urban, industrial, tourism, and services development, and trying to link these activities to each other to finally be a project that has the ability to continue and face economic and international crises.
- 6- Attracting local and foreign private investments to contribute to supporting development and creating an appropriate climate.
- 7- Addressing the problem of unemployment and working to solve it by providing new job opportunities that increase annually.
- 8- Reducing the waves of displaced migration to the major cities and the Nile Valley; the establishment of new urban communities in addition to the Nile Valley Community; and encouraging reverse migration to the south of the Valley and North Sinai.
- 9- Overcoming the erosion of per capita agricultural land and working to close the food gap by doubling the agricultural area.
- 10- Maximizing the use of state resources through the allocation and optimal use of resources in general and agricultural in particular in a way that achieves the comparative advantage of Egyptian agriculture for export, such as natural medicinal herbs.

3.9 National projects in Egypt in the light of Egypt's Vision 2030:

3-9-1 objectives of national projects in Egypt in the vision of Egypt 2030 as an overview of each project:

1. **The Suez Canal Axis development project** aims to maximize the use of the enormous potential of the Suez Canal by establishing a global logistics center and strengthening the road network linking the Suez Canal region with the rest of the Republic's regions, especially transiting this axis. The vision of the project is to make this region an economically integrated, urban, and environmentally balanced region; a distinguished global center in maritime, logistics, industrial, and tourism services; and a participating hub in shaping the contours of world trade by 2030. This project is considered to be high-cost.

- 2- **Establishing the new administrative capital:** it aims to establish a new administrative and Economic City in the Greater Cairo region that includes a residential area, a commercial area and other service areas.
- 3- **The development of four million acres:** it aims to build an integrated community within the new lands, and support the overall goal of the Sustainable Development Strategy: Egypt's Vision 2030, related to increasing the urban area by about 5% of its total area by 2030, in addition to its impact on supporting economic diversity and providing productive and decent job opportunities and emphasizing the participation of all governorates of the Republic in achieving sustainable inclusive growth, this project includes an integrated agricultural - industrial orientation for specific crops, vegetables and fruits, and providing the required facilities for packaging and manufacturing products, and the land will be allocated in the form of suitable among large, medium and small enterprises.
- 4- **Sinai Investment and Development Company:** the project aims to develop Sinai and turn it into an advanced integrated development society that exploits its competitive advantages and natural, human and agricultural resources within the framework of the Suez Canal Axis development project. The project contributes to the absorption and redistribution of human resources in Egypt by investing in labor-intensive sectors to provide job opportunities for the people of Sinai and attract a dense population from the canal and Valley governorates.
- 5- **North-West Coast development project:** the project aims to develop the north-west coast by establishing a set of roads and transverse and longitudinal axes between that region and the rest of the governorates of the Republic in order to strengthen the road and transport network in order to facilitate the movement of the population and employment and achieve the spread of population, trade and various economic activities. It also plays an important role in solving the problem of energy shortage through the generation of electricity by solar energy, in addition to generating electricity through nuclear energy in the Dabaa area. This project extends from the city of El Alamein to the city of Slalom (about 500 km and a depth of 380 km).
- 6- **The Golden Triangle of mineral wealth in southern Egypt:** the project aims to create a new economic zone in Upper Egypt by establishing an integrated global centre (industrial – economic – commercial – logistics – tourism) to achieve sustainable development in Upper Egypt, and it is planned that this project will be implemented in 6 stages, each stage taking 5 years.
- 7- **New development axis:** the project aims to develop about 5 thousand km of roads, which represents about 20.4% of the currently existing roads, estimated at about 24,000 km. In addition to the development of surrounding areas, the project was completed in two stages. The first stage included approximately 3,400 km and was completed in September 2015, and the remainder was completed by the end of 2016.
- 8- **The axis of June 30 and the new city of Galala:** the project aims to establish the axis of June 30, which starts from the International Coastal Road south of Port Said to the Cairo-Ismailia desert road, and it is planned to complete the road to intersect with the Cairo-Suez

Road and reach the Wadi Hajoul tunnel on the Cairo-Ain Sokhna road, passing through the city of Galala. The city of Galala is located on top of the Jalala Mountain in the eastern desert on the Gulf of Suez at an altitude of 700 m. The city is located on an area of 17 thousand acres.

- 9- **Completion of the fourth stage of the third line and the fourth line of the subway:** the fourth stage extends from Haroun station in Heliopolis in a tunnel track to the station of Nozha 1, with a length of 5.15 km, and then in an overhead track to the station of Peace (Chancellor Adly Mansour), near the tenth stop, with a length of 6.37 km, and another branch from Haroun station to the Passenger Terminal 3 at Cairo airport in a tunnel track with a length of 5.65 km, bringing the total length of the stage to 18.17 km and the number of 15 stations. As for the fourth line (6 October/Fustat/New Cairo), which connects the city of 6 October with the centre of the metro network, it provides a passenger transport service and connects it to the densely populated areas of Al-Haram, Faisal, Al-Amraniya and Giza.
- 10- **Construction of one million housing units under the social housing program:** the project aims to provide one million housing units for social housing for low-income citizens in all governorates at a total cost of 150 billion pounds within five years, so the Egyptian government issued the social housing law, under which the social housing fund was established, which aims to reduce the cost burden borne by the state for the construction of these units.
- 11- **Reducing inflationary pressures to stabilize macroeconomic conditions:** by establishing many storage and logistics centers to reduce inflationary pressures by 2030.
- 12- **Specialized industrial clusters for small and medium industries:** as a development solution to support industrial integration between large factories on one hand and small and medium-sized factories on the other, and to contribute to increasing industrial added value, providing job opportunities for women, youth, and people with disabilities, connecting small and medium-sized enterprises to value chains, production, and trade, and developing a set of green economy projects over the next ten years
- 13- **Rubiki Leather City:** establishing an attractive city for the national industry by encouraging the transfer of existing tanneries in the El Ayoun area to the new city and increasing the added value of the Egyptian product and its development in order to achieve competitiveness in the global markets by 2030.
- 14- **Furniture City of Damietta:** aims to increase the proportion of furniture exports from 2% of the global market volume to 8%.
- 15- **Development of industrial zones in the Suez Canal axis:** the strategic direction aims to intensify the effort to exploit the privileged location of the Suez Canal axis industrially to ensure that Egypt is a pivotal Center where the economic package is distributed by expanding the development and establishment of industrial zones in the Suez Canal axis by 2025.

- 16- **Establishing clusters for agricultural industries:** it aims to expand agricultural industries and support exports in this sector by empowering the Centers of agricultural industries and creating the appropriate environment for the establishment of these industries. It also aims to achieve integration between the agricultural sector and the industrial sector, raise the added value in irrigation water and agricultural crops by creating a relationship between farms and factories and increasing the economic value of agricultural products. this program is considered a high cost.
- 17- **Increasing the agricultural area and supporting agricultural industrialization:** working to increase the area of the agricultural area and encouraging investments in the fields of agricultural industrialization.
- 18- **Development of aquaculture projects:** the project aims to promote and facilitate investment in fish farming activities in order to reduce the challenges of self-sufficiency in food, reduce Egypt's import bill of fish, and build on Egypt's competitive advantage from the availability of inputs necessary for this activity (water, land, and labor).
- 19- **The establishment of new urban complexes** to achieve integrated development, including the one and a half million-acre development and reclamation project (the new Egyptian countryside), the project to complete the national structure for the development of North Sinai at the helm of 400 thousand acres (El-Salam canal), and the Sheikh Zayed canal completion project in the southern valley at the helm of 540 thousand acres (Toshka).
- 20- **A programme for the development of covered drainage networks:** providing 100 thousand acres of covered drainage networks through construction, replacement, and renovation projects, in addition to finishing industrial works of cabarets, buckets, hydrants, etc., and providing 480 thousand acres of covered drainage networks by the end of 2017/2018.
- Expansion of public drainage and covered drainage projects to expand and deepen public open banks in new and reclaimed areas to add a 10-thousand-acre lead in 2015/2016 and a 44-thousand-acre lead in 2017/2018, which covered a 25 thousand acre lead.
- 21- **Establishment of archaeological museums in the cities of Sharm el-Sheikh and Hurghada;** introducing a new product aimed at attracting frequent beach visitors and tourists in Sharm el-Sheikh and Hurghada to consume cultural products.
- 22- **Establishing eco-friendly health resorts:** exploiting local natural assets such as oases and therapeutic water eyes to attract visitors from high-spending segments in medical and natural tourism, and this project is considered high-cost.
- 23- **Establishing a racetrack and sports championship arenas:** exploiting the vast lands available in the tourist areas to carry out complementary projects to attract the tourism of the world sports championships. This project is very expensive.
- 24- **Establishing tourist and residential communities in the north coast:** establishing tourist communities in large areas that contain all the living requirements and providing high-

quality facilities to attract foreign and Arab families to spend long-term vacations in Egypt. This project has a high cost.

- 25- **Establishing training center's according to international standards:** building training center's to provide training programmes designed specifically to develop the necessary skills for workers in the tourism sector, and this project comes at a high cost.
- 26- **Establishing the Global Logistics Center for the trade, circulation, and industry of cereals, crops, and food commodities in Damietta:** This project aims to transform Egypt into a Global Logistics Center for the trading, storage, and manufacturing of all value-added activities related to grain, which include manufacturing, packing, and packaging of cereals and seeds, producing oils, as well as oil refining, refining raw sugar, and other related foodstuffs, which are strategic goods and products, thereby achieving food security for Egypt and the countries of the region.
- 27- **The development and implementation of a number of Shoun projects** amounting to 105 Shoun, and the connection of the Shoun with electronic operating systems with a high level of accuracy ensures the safety and follow-up of those Shoun and the wheat they contain.
- 28- **Grain silos projects:** UAE-funded silos project: the project is a huge addition to the storage capacities available in the country.
- 29- **Italian debt swap projects:** work on the establishment of (10) horizontal silos, (2) logistics areas, and (1) vertical silos.
- 30- **Establishing a new generation of new cities on the axes of national development roads:** it aims to establish the new administrative capital east of Cairo, the new city of El Alamein, the new city of Toshka, the new city of Farafra and the city of East Port Said.
- 31- **Developing and extending the road network to serve development purposes:** developing the existing road network in a way that facilitates the movement of citizens and goods throughout the Republic and improves connectivity indicators.
- 32- **Daba'a nuclear power plant:** it aims to diversify the current energy mix, which depends on up to 96% of natural gas and petroleum products, so as to reduce dependence on these sources and switch to renewable energy from nuclear sources.

4-3 The strategy of national projects in Egypt in the Vision of Egypt 2030: The strategy of national projects relies on many elements in order to reach and exit this set of projects that are the nucleus of development in Egypt, and we summarize the elements of the strategy as follows:

- The concept of sustainable development in its three dimensions is specific to the axes of the strategy.
- Building on the above and taking advantage of pioneering experiences.
- Participatory methodology for the preparation of the strategy.
- Stages of strategy preparation:

- The preliminary stage is the first stage.
- The second stage: preparation of the main directions.
- The third stage: the selection of priority policies and programs.
- The fourth stage: preparation of the strategy document and community dialogue.
- Choose performance measurement Indicators.
- Identify quantitative targets and challenges that may be faced to achieve them.
- Selection of models for programmes and projects.
- Challenges of financing the strategy.
- The governing framework of the strategy.

5- Global models of strategic management:

Many experiences of different countries have been studied and come up with the benefit of each experience in planning and managing national projects as follows:

5-1 United States of America: Civil society is an effective force and plays a major role in strategic urban planning.

5-2 Europe: the importance of producing an integrated intelligent geographic information system and a representation of virtual reality that can be used in planning events.

5-3 France: the importance of developing a planning method based on modern trends in strategic urban planning.

5-4 Kosovo: - Strategic urban planning based on partnership can set priorities and direct resources.

- The partnership of the general public in decision-making establishes the rules of transparency and responsibility of decision-makers towards stakeholders and helps to fair and efficient allocation of resources and their use in their designated areas.

5-5 Australia: Progress is based on reform, reorganization, and revision of the assessment of existing resources rather than attention to their expansion.

5-6 Asia: the importance of geographic information devices and the accompanying spatial data infrastructures

- The trend has changed from carrying out specific projects to comprehensive and general real estate development, and the tasks of urban planning have changed from partial planning to planning and management.

- Flexible and adaptable methods should be used in planning in order to obtain the greatest benefit from them and ensure that they are appropriate to the existing conditions, which requires strengthening technical knowledge with a strong focus on structuring issues, critical and strategic thinking, and understanding of political content.

5.7 Russia: During strategic planning, the direct active participation of citizens must be adhered to.

5.8 South America:

- The importance of large-scale diversification in mobilizing new sources of financing for projects.
- The significance of a favourable political environment.
- The importance of finding appropriate monitoring and follow-up systems
- The importance of the determination of local executives, the existence of an institutional framework and the partnership of the main forces, the high technical capacity of the participating parties
- The importance of consensus among stakeholders who will play an important role in the implementation.

5.9 Africa:

5.9.1 Kenya:

The Comprehensive Partnership method should be adopted in the planning process and in the development of operational plans, and strategic plans should pay attention to sensory, political, environmental, social, and economic issues, as well as set a vision for long-term development.

5.9.2 Morocco: a method must be developed to ensure partnership at the highest level.

- The importance of coordination between the branches and interests of the government to ensure the compatibility of local economic development plans and their integration into a broader framework
- The importance of there is an urgent need to develop a national training programme for elected officials and their employees locally and anywhere.
- It is important to provide local authorities with the necessary mechanisms and systems to carry out participatory strategic planning processes and implement local development plans.

5.10 South Korea:

- Strategies in all fields must be studied efficiently in their aspects, and all elements of the strategy should be studied in detail, supported by evidence, studies, and figures.
- Civil society plays an important role in the preparation of national projects, no less important than decision-makers.
- The responses of the authorities responsible for the projects should be by the necessary means leading to the purpose.

6- A proposed urban strategy for the management of national projects in Egypt

The proposed strategy for the management of national projects is divided into three main sections according to the stages of the project as follows:

First stage: The project planning stage (pre-project implementation):

First: General considerations: such as

- Adopting the concept of sustainable development as a general framework intended to improve the quality of life at present in a way that does not prejudice the rights of future generations to a better life.

- The strategy should include a strategic goal and sub-goals, performance measurement indicators, quantitative targets planned to achieve the goals, knowledge of the expected challenges, the necessary programmes and projects, the priority of their implementation, and their chronology.

- The challenges that guide development processes must be taken into account and even turned into catalysts for development instead of challenges.

- **Strategy preparation stages:** Strategy development must go through four basic stages:

- **Preparatory stage:** analysis of the current situation and previous strategies at the national and sectoral levels; civil society and private sector strategies and visions; international strategies; analysis of current and future challenges; and familiarization with international challenges.

- **The "preparing the main directions" stage:** in this stage, the strategy's main directions are determined, its main structure is developed, the axes it includes, and the visions, goals, and sub-goals of the axes are formulated.

- **The third stage,** where priority policies and programs are selected, where the sub-goals of the various axes are converted into priority policies, programs and projects, and making sure that the axes are interconnected with each other in an integrated and comprehensive framework for Sustainable Development. Also, during this stage, performance indicators are reviewed that measure progress towards achieving all the objectives of the strategy and determine the quantitative targets for these indicators.

This is followed by identifying the programs and projects proposed to be implemented to address the challenges that are selected, and this is done by organizing workshops, and preparing identification cards for these programs that include all the details of these programs.

The main body responsible for the implementation of each element of policies, programs and projects and the participating parties that also play a role in the implementation of these policies, programs or projects are also identified.

- **The fourth stage "preparation of the strategy document and community dialogue":** will see the strategy document prepared and reviewed with all interested parties; a plan for community communication prepared; the strategy's implementation announced at the national

and regional levels; and a conference organized under the auspices of senior state officials and with the participation of all development partners to announce the strategy.

- The state's role is concentrated on more effectively implementing its role as a regulator, in developing policies, setting standards, monitoring and monitoring, and creating a general climate for both private sector institutions and civil society to play the roles assigned to them as key partners in development.

Second: the participation of civil society: -civil society has an effective force; it plays a big role in strategic urban planning.

- Strategic urban planning, including a selective approach and a practical approach based on partnership, can identify priorities and direct resources to meet those priorities.

Third: the participation of the main forces, stakeholders and those affected: the implementation of strategic urban plans requires a great effort that includes a consensus dialogue between stakeholders who will play an important role in the implementation; clear rules of conduct must be established; and the roles of different parties in the planning, implementation, monitoring, and review processes must be respected.

Fourth: the use of modern technology: It is important to provide local authorities with the necessary mechanisms and systems to carry out participatory strategic planning and the implementation of local development plans; these systems include systems for monitoring and controlling performance and effectively managing and mobilizing human and financial resources.

Fifth: the use of modern trends: a planning method based on modern trends in strategic urban planning should be developed at the theoretical and practical levels, and the developed method is based on the means of theoretical systems of deduction, trial and error that are used in overlapping issues, with the introduction of elements of modern ideas in planning and ideal design stemming from strategic considerations.

Sixth: using flexible methods in strategy and enhancing technical knowledge:

- It is necessary to switch from using rigid mechanisms to flexible methods that are easy to adapt in order to obtain the greatest benefit from them and ensure that they are appropriate to the existing conditions. Through this, it became clear that setting an agenda for planning for Sustainable Development necessarily requires strengthening the basic areas of technical knowledge with a strong focus on structuring issues, critical and strategic thinking, and understanding the political and institutional contents.

- Strategies in all fields should be studied in all aspects, and all elements of the strategy should be studied in detail, supported by evidence, studies, and figures, through:

- **From an environmental, archaeological, and historical point of view**, such as: the habitat of some migratory animals or birds; fog; land subsidence; pollution of water bodies; impact on water quality; the habitat of some rare plants; or impact on buildings or historical areas.

- **In terms of economic feasibility and securing financial resources**, such as the economic feasibility of the project due to its high material cost, insufficient resources, impact on other priority projects, or low investment value.

- **In terms of achieving a balance between regional development and social justice, or the feasibility of sites**, such as: causing unbalanced regional development due to the concentration of population and industries in some areas, affecting emerging industries that require access to them, or not benefiting certain social strata from projects, or the inability of the project to produce the intended effects due to the choice of an inappropriate location in terms of geography, meteorology, accessibility, or the impact of the project on a certain category of society.

- **The lack of technologies**, such as: the ineffectiveness of new technology in achieving the intended functions when combined with the low level of local technology, or dependence on other countries in technology and project operation.

- **On the political motive side**, such as: winning more votes in elections or serving categories at the expense of other categories, from both short and long-term perspectives; presenting them transparently to officials; consulting and understanding with them in the smallest details of the strategy; receiving the responses of officials; studying them in detail; and then presenting them again to officials; and so on until reaching a complete picture of the strategy.

Seventh: benefit from previous experiences: the strategy should be based on taking advantage of the leading experiences, whether within the same country or at the international level, to identify the success factors and benefit from these experiences, and from distinguished international practices in the field of development in general and sustainable development in particular.

Eighth: finding a monitoring and follow-up system:

- The importance of finding appropriate monitoring and follow-up systems, such as developing a system of urban indicators used to emphasise the tangible impact of strategic plan projects.

- The strategy should include indicators to measure performance and take into account that they are specific and measurable and can be achieved in the light of available resources and existing conditions in a specific time frame.

- When choosing performance measurement indicators, it should be taken into account not to confuse performance measurement indicators with the proposed initiatives and the need for a logical link between the indicators of measuring inputs, outputs and results to ensure the achievement of the strategic objectives of each axis and the creation of a performance follow-up system.

Ninth: finding flexible financing plans: the importance of supporting strategic urban plans with annual investment plans, in which there are national laws, standards, guidelines, and technical guidelines for strategic partnership in municipal planning.

-We must rely on innovative and diverse means and tools in financing.

Tenth: coordination between all the authorities responsible for the strategy and its implementation:

- The importance of supporting efforts to strengthen coordination between the branches and interests of the government to ensure that local economic development plans are harmonized and integrated into a broader framework. As coordination should be at the national level, coordination at the regional level is important, as the regional level is large enough to include a large segment of people and a variety of issues, and it is small enough in a way that confirms the commitment of the current reality in the different communities that make up the region.
- The responses of the responsible authorities in the meetings and workshops about the projects should be by the following means:
 - Providing objective and scientific persuasion data and complementary measures
 - Multilateral consultative bodies should be formed that include key stakeholders.
 - Activities must be promoted to convince the public and residents and form a consensus.
 - The responses of the government officials should be direct and restore the delayed process.
 - Resumption of pending projects based on active responses to lawsuits.

Second phase: the project implementation phase

First: project preparation: these operations are carried out to identify a new project or a new stage in an already existing project with the aim of starting the project. At this stage, a project start-up permit is obtained, the initial scope of the project and the financial resources necessary for the start-up operations are determined, and internal and external stakeholders influencing the results of the project are also identified.

Second, project planning:

- 1- Comprehend the project's scope.
- 2- Define the objectives of the project.
- 3- Data and information collection and analysis
- 4- Project scheduling.

Third: the stage of approval and approval of the plan

- 1- Generate the plan in its final form.
- 2- Correcting weaknesses and flaws in the plan.
- 3- Present the plan to senior management.
- 4- The presence of an integrated technical apparatus capable of making decisions related to the planning process.

Fourth: project implementation:

1- Directing and managing the implementation of the project, namely:

- Delegation of authority to qualified individuals.
- Clarify the plan and explain it to the employees.
- The manager in this depends on the approved policies, procedures, and rules.

2- **Managing the expectations of stakeholders, namely:** the process of communicating with them to achieve their requirements.

3- **Procurement management process:** to ensure the provision of the required resources from suppliers for the implementation process.

Fifth: monitoring and follow-up of the project during implementation: The follow-up process is usually carried out through:

- 1- Availability of technical staff.
- 2- Go over the plan again.
- 3- Evaluate the implementation
- 4- External circumstances.

Sixth: closing the project: these are the processes for terminating the project and identifying the lessons learned, which are carried out to terminate the activities in all project processes: identifying the lessons learned, saving all project documents, and closing the procurement.

Third phase: evaluation and follow-up (post-project implementation)

The process of systematically and objectively measuring the suitability, performance, and success of ongoing and completed projects, where the assessment is a management tool to guide decision makers and project managers on whether the project planning and implementation have gone as planned based on the following three inputs:

- Assessment of objectives
- Action evaluation.
- Evaluation of results.

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